

Notes

Thermodynamic Stability Constants of the Aluminium (III) Complexes with Salicylic Acid and Sulfosalicylic Acid

ARUN P. JOSHI

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur

Manuscript received 20 April 1972; received 14 March 1973;
accepted 29 March 1974

ALUMINIUM is known to form complexes with salicylic acid¹⁻⁶ and sulfosalicylic acid⁷. The values of stability constants obtained by potentiometric method⁸ and spectrophotometric method⁷ the two complexes respectively are also known.

Oniciu, Schmidt and Cadariu studied aluminosalicylates and aluminosulfosalicylates and have reported formation constants using Bjerrum potentiometric titration method.⁹

The present work was carried out to study the complexing property of aluminium with salicylic acid and sulfosalicylic acid. Potentiometric studies were made at four different fixed values of ionic strength. In the present communication are reported for the first time the "practical" proton-ligand stability constants at various ionic concentrations and the thermodynamic metal-ligand stability constant (stepwise) obtained by the Bjerrum-Calvin titration technique as used by Irving and Rossotti¹⁰⁻¹².

Experimental :

Materials

Metal solution : A stock solution of Al (III) (0.02M) was prepared by dissolving a known weight of potassium aluminium sulphate (AnalaR Grade) in calculated quantity of nitric acid solution to prevent hydrolysis.

Ligand solution : Solutions of salicylic acid and sulfosalicylic acid were prepared just before the experiment by dissolving known weights of the acids in alcohol. The solutions of the ligands, required in the experiment, were prepared by suitable dilution of the stock solutions. In actual experiment, the mixtures were prepared in such a way that ligands were present in 5% alcoholic solution. The solutions of the acids were standardized potentiometrically.

Sodium hydroxide : Sodium hydroxide (Merck) was dissolved in CO₂ free distilled water. The solution was kept overnight. A small portion of it was diluted and its concentration was determined by titrating it potentiometrically against standard (0.1M) potassium hydrogen phthalate.

Potassium nitrate : Potassium nitrate solution was used to maintain the ionic strength of the system and

was prepared by dissolving a known weight of AnalaR Grade in CO₂ free distilled water.

Nitric acid : The stock solution of nitric acid (0.1M) was prepared by diluting a known volume of AnalaR nitric acid. Its concentration was determined by titrating potentiometrically against standard sodium hydroxide solution.

Apparatus : A pH meter (Electronics Corporation of India, Limited) with glass-calomel electrode system was used for pH measurements. The sensitivity of the instrument is ± 0.05 . The pH meter was calibrated by a suitable buffer before use.

All experiments were carried out at room temperature (27°).

Bjerrum-Calvin titration :

The three mixtures were prepared as follows A : $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ HNO₃, B : $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ HNO₃ + $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand, C : $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ HNO₃ + $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ metalion solution, such that concentrations of common ingredients were identical in different cases. An appropriate quantity of potassium nitrate solution was added to maintain the desired ionic strength i.e. $\mu = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3$ and 0.4 . The final volume in all the cases was 100 ml. The ratio between metal and ligand was 1:5. These solutions were titrated with standard sodium hydroxide solution. Three titration curves were obtained. They were referred to as (a) acid titration curve, (b) ligand titration curve and (c) complex titration curve.

Proton-Ligand Stability Constants :

In order to calculate the formation constants of the metal chelates, it is necessary to have the knowledge of proton-ligand stability constant. The values of $\bar{n}_A$ at various pH have been calculated from the acid and ligand titration curves. Equation (1) as used by Irving and Rossotti¹² was employed for calculations.

$$\bar{n}_A = yT^o_{CL} + \frac{(V' - V'')(N + E^o)}{(V^o + V')} \Big/ T^o_{CL} \quad \dots (1)$$

where V'' and V' denote the volume of alkali to reach the same pH in the titration of ligand and acid respectively; T^o_{CL} is the total ligand concentration, y the total number of replaceable protons attached to the ligand, N the normality of alkali and E^o the initial concentration of the free acid. $\bar{n}_A$ is the average number of protons attached per ligand ion.

The calculation of the protonation constant was carried out by plotting a graph of $\bar{n}_A$ against pH then applying the method of interpolation at half $\bar{n}_A$ values.

Salicylic acid : The formation curves extend between 0 and 2 in the $\bar{n}_A$ scale indicating dissociation of H_2SA as follows.

Sulfosalicylic acid : The formation curves extend between 0 and 2 in the $\bar{n}_A$ scale indicating dissociation of H_2SA as follows.

The values at various ionic strengths having the error limit of ± 0.03 are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1. VALUES OF THE PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF THE LIGANDS, TEMP. = 27°C

Ligand	Constants	$\mu = 0.1$	$\mu = 0.2$	$\mu = 0.3$	$\mu = 0.4$
Salicylic acid	$\log K_1^H$	11.65	11.53	11.42	11.31
	$\log K_2^H$	2.06	1.98	1.90	11.82
	$\log \beta^H$	13.71	13.51	13.32	13.13
Sulfosalicylic acid	$\log K_1^H$	11.75	11.67	11.52	11.40
	$\log K_2^H$	2.12	2.03	1.94	1.84
	$\log \beta^H$	13.87	13.70	13.46	13.24

Metal-Ligand Stability Constants :

For metal complex or chelate formation taking place in steps in a homogeneous solution, the step formation constants are given by equation (2)

$$K_n = \frac{C_{MLn}}{C_M C_L^{n-1} C_L} \quad (n = 1, 2, \dots, N) \quad \dots (2)$$

where K_n is called n th metal-ligand stability constant.

In the present case, the formation constants have been obtained by the analysis of formation curves obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ against pL . The value of $\bar{n}$, the average number of ligands attached per metal ion is calculated by equation (3).

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(V'' - V')(N + E^0)}{(V^0 + V'')\bar{n}_A T^0_{cm}} \quad \dots (3)$$

where T^0_{CM} denotes the total concentration of the metal present in solution and other terms have their usual meanings

The free ligand exponent pL has been calculated by equation (4).

$$pL = \log_{10} \left[\frac{\sum_{n=0}^{n=N} \beta_n^H \left\{ \frac{1}{\text{anti log } pH} \right\} \frac{V^0 + V''}{V^0}}{T^0_{CL} - \bar{n} T^0_{cm}} \right] \quad (4)$$

where β_n^H is overall proton ligand stability constant

The formation curves obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ against pL were analysed as usual and various computational methods¹³ were applied to evaluate the stepwise formation constants. The results obtained are in good agreement with each other. The error limits are ± 0.03 for $\log K_1$ and ± 0.05 for $\log K_2$.

Aluminium (III)-SA and Aluminium (III)-SSA

In both these cases the metal curves did not join up parallel with the ligand curve indicating the liberation of extra protons due to hydrolysis of metal ions. Precipitation was observed for salicylic acid at pH 6.0. Hence, only lower pH regions of the titration curves were used for calculation in order to avoid the error due to hydrolysis. For sulfo-salicylic acid also the calculations were made below pH 6.0. The values of the concentration stability constants at various ionic strengths are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2. VALUES OF CONCENTRATION STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES TEMP. = 27°C

System	Constants	$\mu = 0.1$	$\mu = 0.2$	$\mu = 0.3$	$\mu = 0.4$
Al(III)-Salicylic acid	$\log K_1$	12.38	12.22	12.08	11.94
	$\log K_2$	10.61	10.48	10.30	10.17
	$\log \beta$	22.99	22.70	22.38	22.11
Al(III)-Sulfosalicylic acid	$\log K_1$	12.26	12.12	11.98	11.83
	$\log K_2$	8.75	8.60	8.46	8.30
	$\log \beta$	21.01	20.72	20.44	20.13

Thermodynamic Stability Constants :

The thermodynamic formation constants were obtained by extrapolation of the measured formation constants to zero ionic strength¹⁴. The value obtained for Al(III)-SA complex is 23.4 and for Al(III)-SSA complex 21.3

The values of stability constant for Al(III)-SA system are more than Al(III)-SSA system indicating that Al(III)-SA complex is more stable. This may be due to $-SO_3H$ group present in sulfosalicylic acid which causes steric hindrance thereby decreasing the stability of the complex.

Acknowledgement :

Thanks are due to Prof. R. H. Sahasrabudhey, Head, Chemistry Department, Nagpur University, Nagpur for encouragement

References :

- H. BABKO and T. N. RYCHKOVA, *Zhur. Obshchei. Khim.*, 1948, 13, 1617
- B. DAS and S. ADITYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 36, 473.
- J. PECCI and W. O. FOYE, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc. Sci. Ed.*, 1960, 49, 411.
- I. CADARIU and L. ONICIU, *Acad. Rep. populare Romne, Filiala Cluj. Studii Cercetari Chem.*, 1959, 10, 113; 1961, 12(1), 69.
- V. I. KUZNETSOV and N. R. BASARGIN, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1962, 7, 814.
- A. K. RAI, R. K. MEHROTRA and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1963, 20, 105
- R. K. NANDA and S. ADITYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 34, 577; 1963, 40, 660

NOTES

8. L. HAVELKOVA and M. BARTUSCK, *Collect. Czech Chem. Commun.*, 1969, 34, 3722.
9. L. ONICIU, E. SCHMIDT and I. CADARIU, *Rev. Roumaine Chim.*, 1964, 9, 849.
10. J. BJERRUM, Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution. Hasse, Copenhagen, 1941.
11. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.
12. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
13. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
14. F. J. C. ROSSOTTI and H. ROSSOTTI, The Determination of Stability Constants., McGraw-Hill, New York, 1961.

The kinetics of the decarboxylation of oxanilic acid in resorcinol and catechol

M. A. HALEEM, M. A. HAKEEM* and I. SALAMH**

Engineering College, University of Riyadh, Riyadh: Saudi Arabia.

Manuscript received 10 November 1972, accepted 4 April 1974

IT is well known that the first two members of the homologous series of dicarboxylic acids, malonic and oxalic acids, readily undergo decarboxylation in many solvents. Fraenkel et al¹ established the mechanism of decarboxylation of both the acids on the basis of their kinetic studies. The author studied the decarboxylation of malonic² and oxalic³ acids in resorcinol and catechol in his earlier investigations. Clark studied the decarboxylation of oxanilic acid in aniline, *o*-Toluidine⁴ and in several ethers⁵, reporting that oxanilic acid decomposes by the same mechanism as followed by malonic and oxalic acids. Since oxanilic acid is a mono-derivative of oxalic acid, it was of interest to study the decarboxylation of oxanilic acid in resorcinol and catechol, in order to ascertain whether or not it follows the same mechanism as followed by oxalic and malonic acids.

Experimental :

Materials :

Oxanilic acid used was of E Merck (Darmstadt). m.p. = 150° stored over chemically pure magnesium perchlorate. Resorcinol and catechol used were BDH analytical reagents. No further purification of these chemicals was done.

Apparatus and Technique :

The kinetic experiments were conducted in a constant temperature oil-bath ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) by measuring the volume of carbon dioxide gas evolved at constant pressure. The apparatus and technique are the same as described in our previous articles⁶⁻⁷. A weighed amount of oxanilic acid (0.2-0.3g) was taken and dropped in the molten solvent (50g resorcinol), and in another set of 50g catechol. The carbon dioxide gas was collected at room temperature in the gas burette filled with water previously saturated with carbon dioxide. Duplicate experimental runs were

made and the deviation in the results was within $\pm 1.32\%$ in resorcinol and $\pm 1.55\%$ in catechol.

TABLE 1. APPARENT FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE DECARBOXYLATION OF OXANILIC ACID IN RESORCINOL AND CATECHOL

Temperature °C	Av. $k_1 \times 10^4$ sec ⁻¹ .	Av. $k_1 \times 10^4$ Sec ⁻¹
	Resorcinol	Catechol
140	6.91	7.01
150	11.48	11.48
155	19.50	17.78
160	32.36	26.92
165	53.70	31.62
170	91.20	63.10

TABLE 2. COMPARISON OF THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

	Resorcinol		Catechol	
	Oxanilic acid	Oxalic ^a acid	Oxanilic acid	Oxalic ^a acid
Log A, (Sec ⁻¹)	16.46	12.66	12.82	9.50
E _a , kcal mole ⁻¹	37.58	28.99	30.58	23.80
ΔF [‡] , kcal mole ⁻¹	30.62	31.39	30.81	31.21
ΔS [‡] , cal. mole ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹	16.06	-5.85	-0.58	-17.93
ΔH [‡] , kcal. mole ⁻¹	36.72	28.07	29.72	22.89

^a Reference 3.

Results and Discussion :

The rate of decarboxylation of oxanilic acid was measured in resorcinol and catechol at six temperatures in the range 140°-170°. The plot of $\log (V_\infty - V_t)$ vs t was linear in almost all the experiments indicating that the reaction is first order, where V_∞ is the volume of carbon dioxide after completion of the reaction and V_t is the volume at any time t . The average rate constants calculated from the slopes of the experimental logarithmic plots are shown in Table 1. The rate of decarboxylation of oxanilic acid in resorcinol and catechol at 140° and 150° is the same. Above 150° faster rates have been observed in resorcinol than in catechol. The decarboxylation rates of malonic, oxalic, benzoic, and substituted benzoic acids are lower in catechol than in resorcinol at all temperatures. Due to this abnormal behaviour several experimental runs were made and the results were quite reproducible.

The lower rates at 140°-150° indicate that at these temperatures only one hydroxyl group of catechol forms the hydrogen bonding with the carbonyl group of the oxanilic acid. Above 150° the other carbonyl group of the oxanilic acid associates with the other hydroxyl group of the catechol, and a bulkier intermediate complex causes the slow decomposition. It has been reported that the decarboxylation is faster in acidic than in basic medium. In the present study, even if catechol is more acidic than resorcinol, it is found that this general rule is not obeyed. However, the slow rates for the decarboxylation of oxanilic acid in catechol are due to an intermediate com-

* Lecturer, Engg. College, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.

**Lecturer City College, Hyderabad, India.